

Cult at the Athenian Agora

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Entry tags: Agora, Monument, Religious Place, Greek Religions, Greek Cult, Graeco-Roman, Aegean, Archaeological site, Religious Group, Attica, Greece, Sacred Enclosure

An agora was a communal space found in most Greek cities that contained religious structures alongside those with commercial and civic functions, but it can also be thought of as a quasi-religious space in its own right. Specific points of religious focus within the Agora in Athens include, for example, the Altar of the Twelve Gods, a temple to Apollo Patroos, an altar to Aphrodite Ourania, the crossroads enclosure, and the Metroon. In addition, the Archon Basileus, the official in charge of religious festivals, had his headquarters in the Stoa Basileus; a calendar for sacrifices was inscribed on a wall there. Religion was embedded within the political institutions, so when governing bodies met in a building like the tholos or bouleterion there were ritual actions to start the meetings. Images of gods and heroes were present in herms and monuments like that to the Eponymous Heroes. The area as a whole was marked by horoi (boundary stones) and those who could pollute it were banned (e.g., murders), similar to other kinds of religious space. Although the political roles of the Athenian Agora began to wain in the Hellenistic period and were transformed by the Roman, it was still used for religion, as we can see by the importing of temples from elsewhere in Attica presumably for use in Imperial Cult there.

Date Range: 600 BCE - 276 CE

Region: Agora of Athens

Region tags: Greece, Attica

The Agora (central marketplace) of ancient Athens

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Camp, J.M. *The Athenian Agora: Excavations in the Heart of Classical Athens* (Thames & Hudson 1986).

– Source 2: Camp, J.M. *Gods and Heroes in the Athenian Agora. Agora Picture Book 19* (American School of Classical Studies at Athens 1980)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://agora.ascsa.net/research>

- Source 1 Description: Online database of the excavations of the Athenian Agora
- Source 2 URL: <http://agora.ascsa.net/id/agora/publication/agora%20picture%20book%2019>
- Source 2 Description: Images and pdf of Camp, J.M. Gods and Heroes in the Athenian Agora.
- Source 1 URL: <https://topostext.org/place/380237XAgo>
- Source 1 Description: ToposText entry on Agora of Athens

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1931-41, 1945-present

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavations of the Athenian Agora (American School of Classical Studies at Athens)

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1895-97

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: excavations by German Archaeological Institute

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range: 1859-1912

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: excavations by the Greek Archaeological Society

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: Eridanos River runs through north end

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature
– Leveling of ground
– Terracing
– Trackway or road-surface
– Water feature
– Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– Yes
Notes: boundaries marked by horos stones

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Eponymous Heroes Monument

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Political

– Memorial

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– I don't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

Notes: references to the monument go back to the 5th c. BCE, but the excavated structure is only 4th

↳ In antiquity
– Once

– Yes

Notes: Altar to the Twelve Gods

↳ A single structure
– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Square

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Political

Notes: political associations through its original dedicant

– Sacrificial

– Other [specify]: functional: starting point for measuring distances from Athens

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: early version destroyed in Persian invasion; later version unsure

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of war

Notes: the earlier version; later version unknown

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

– Yes

Notes: temple to Apollo Patroos

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: earlier archaic version seems to have been apsidal

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Political

Notes: as Apollo Patroos ("ancestral") he's important for identity formation

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: I don't know

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: no

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: I don't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

– Yes

Notes: Crossroads Enclosure

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: rocky outcropping

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: possibly both communal and individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: allowed to silt up and go out of use

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: temple of Ares

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Political

Notes: political in the sense of motivations for moving the temple into the Agora in the early Roman period

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– I don't know

Notes: it was, but I don't know how or when

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: moved from other site (Pallene) and reconstructed within the Agora

↳ In antiquity

– Once

– Yes

Notes: altar of Aphrodite Ourania

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
–Other [specify]: unknown

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
–Other [specify]: unknown

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
–Other [specify]: unknown

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

– Yes

Notes: Aiakeion

↳ A single structure
– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Square

↳ One single feature
–Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– I don't know

Notes: yes, but I don't know how/ when

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Stoa Basileus

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Political

– Memorial

Notes: displayed records of dramatic festival winners, sacrificial calendar, laws

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– I don't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: it is not dedicated to supernatural beings, but many are represented/ worshiped there

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: I would not consider the heroes of the Eponymous Heroes Monument to be "non-divine," but others might

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: political official, likely an archaic tyrannos

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 30

Notes: This changes over time: in earlier periods, much of the Agora was available for temporary construction (the market) with the buildings along the edges.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 608

Notes: Temple of Ares (Early Roman, probably early 1st CE) "the width has been variously obtained as 16.76 m., 16.87 m., and 16.95 m., the length as 36.25 m., 36.28 m., and 36.36 m." [Dinsmoor, Hesp. 9 (1940): 9]

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Temple of Ares (fragmentary superstructure)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: too many buildings and too much variety

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: too many buildings and too much variety

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: clay roof tiles

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

|

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: no

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: concrete in some buildings by Roman period

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: not known for all religious buildings in Agora, but definite for some (eg, Temple of Ares)

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: not known for all religious buildings in Agora, but definite for some

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: not known for all religious buildings in Agora, but definite for some (eg, Temple of Ares)

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: certain for Apollo Patroos temple

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: associated with structures like Eponymous Heroes Monument and set up as free-standing monuments all over

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: set up as free-standing monuments all over Agora

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: not known for all religious structures in Agora, but definite for some

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: not known for all religious structures in Agora, but definite for some

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Notes: paintings known for Stoa Poikile

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
– I don't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: unknown

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– No
Notes: I only know of mosaics from private houses in the area

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: none

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Notes: Herms are semi-abstract

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: unknown

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: heroes are previously human and include Aiakos and Eponymous Heroes

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: there is important oath-taking in the Agora, which might count for this

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: through prayer/ sacrifice

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: regular animal sacrifice at altars; purifications using pig sacrifices

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: pyre deposits in workshops

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: unknown

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: none

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Notes: officials are fed at public expense in some of the buildings, but I don't think that is what this question is asking

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: maybe any communal animal sacrifice is "large-scale," but I don't think so

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: no large scale rituals

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: annual sacrifices; other rituals like prayer or cleansing more frequent (e.g, every meeting of boule)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: note especially references in oath of office

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: I am considering the Archon Basileus to be a "religious specialist" for this answer since his major duties include festival maintenance and other religious matters

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

Notes: upper class, but that's more by default than by rule

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Notes: As the seat of the Athenian government, it could be argued that it does, but it is the government, not the place

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: Aiakeion used for grain storage

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Yes

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Place for economic functions (marketplace, standardization of weights and measures, etc.)

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: although there are no "scriptures," there are writings relevant to cult activity such as the calendar of Athenian sacrifices in the Stoa Basileus

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Laura Gawlinski. The Athenian Agora: Museum Guide. ASCSA. isbn: 9780876616581.

Reference: John Camp. The Athenian Agora: Excavations in the Heart of Classical Athens. Thames & Hudson. isbn: 9780500276839.

Reference: John McK. Camp II. The Athenian Agora. American School of Classical Studies at Athens. isbn: 9780876616574.

Reference: John McK. Camp. The Athenian Agora. ASCSA. isbn: 9780876616437.